

Supplementary Information

Unconventional Single Molecular Conductance Behavior for a New Heterocyclic Anchoring Group: Pyrazolyl

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a. Synthesis of 1,4-bis(1*H*-pyrazol-4-ylethynyl)benzene

1,4-bis(1*H*-pyrazol-4-ylethynyl)benzene, compound **1**, was synthesized according to previously published procedures which were slightly modified.^{1,2} Reactions were carried out in oxygen-free atmosphere using standard Schlenk techniques. Briefly, in a Schlenk dried in the oven, 4-iodo-1(1-ethoxyethyl)-1*H*-pyrazole (2.74 g, 10.3 mmol), copper iodide (0.075 g, 0.39 mmol) and palladium(II)bis(triphenylphosphine) dichloride (0.278 g, 0.39 mmol) were placed along with dry triethylamine (20 mL) and a stirring bar. 1,4-diethynylbenzene (0.50 g, 3.96 mmol) was dissolved in dry trimethylamine (5 mL) under an argon atmosphere and added to the reaction flask by cannulation. The reaction was kept under stirring at 70 °C for 24 h and followed by TLC. Once 1,4-diethynylbenzene was completely consumed, the mixture was cooled down to room temperature, extracted with AcOEt and filtered through a Celite[®] plug, evaporated and washed with deionized water, aqueous ammonium hydroxide (28 % NH₃) and brine. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered, evaporated and purified by silica gel chromatography (AcOEt-hexane 2:3) to obtain the compound bis(ethoxyethyl)-1,4-bis(1*H*-pyrazol-4-ylethynyl)benzene (1.59 g, 81.76 % yield). This intermediate material was deprotected according to reported procedures affording quantitatively the desired product.

¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 7.95 (4H, s), 7.48 (4H, s), 4.56 (broad, 2H). ¹³C-NMR (DMSO-d₆, ppm): 136.6 (CH), 131.6 (CH), 122.5 (C), 100.8 (C), 89.2 (C), 84.0 (C). Elem. Anal. calc. for C₁₆H₁₀N₄ (FW ¼ 258.3 g·mol⁻¹): C, 74.40; H, 3.91; N, 21.69%; found C, 74.18; H, 3.71; N, 21.32%. MS (MALDI-TOF) (DHB): 258 [M]⁺. ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AV-400 (operating at 400 MHz for ¹H and 100 MHz for ¹³C). Mass Spectrometry was performed using an ESI Bruker Esquire 300+, a MALDI+/TOF Bruker Microflex system.

b. Electrical properties

b.1. Experimental details

Solution preparation conditions for single conductance measurements were 1·10⁻⁴ M in anhydrous THF. A clean and flame annealed gold Arrandee[®] commercial substrate was immersed for 1 minute in the sample solution, extracted, washed with ethanol and deionized water, and blown dry with a nitrogen stream before

measurements. Single molecule conductance measurements were performed in dry and deoxygenated mesitylene using an Agilent 5500 Scanning Tunnelling Microscope (STM) controller in conjunction with the Agilent Picoscan 5.3.3 software. STM tips were prepared from commercially available Au wires (99.99%, 0.25 mm diameter, Goodfellow) electrochemically etched in a 1:1 solution of HCl:EtOH at approximately +7.0 V. The widely known STM $I(s)$ technique was used to determine the single molecule conductance.³⁻⁵ Employed parameters to determine the single molecular conductance, were a set-point current (I_0) of 60 nA and a sample bias voltage (V_{bias}) of -0.6 V. The tip was withdrawn from the set-point distance by 4 nm with a duration of the retraction of 0.1 seconds. Scans displaying events were then analysed as described in the main text.

b.2. Traditional plateau-like events

As described in the main body of the paper, $I(s)$ traces in single molecule measurement traditionally show a plateau shape (Figure S1.a). The analysis of plateau-like $I(s)$ curves is also schematically shown in Figure S1.b and it consists on the construction of data histograms where the maximum obtained is recognized as the most probable value for the single molecular conductance.

Figure S1. a) Schematic illustration of the $I(s)$ method where the molecular junction formation and breakage are shown as well as a simulated $I(s)$ trace with a plateau-like event. b) Typical 1D histogram obtained from $I(s)$ data treatment.

b.3. Break-off distance

A break-off distance histogram for compound **1** is shown in Figure S2. To determine the break-off distance the initial tip–substrate distance has been included to h state parameters ($s_0 = 1.2$ nm) and using a 6.9 ± 1.0 nm⁻¹ ($I_0 = 10$ nA; $U_t = 0.6$ V), which was determined by a calibration procedure as previously described.^{6,7} using a $d \ln I / ds$ value of 6.9 ± 1.0 nm⁻¹ ($I_0 = 10$ nA; $U_t = 0.6$ V). The obtained break-off distance, 1.55 ± 0.1 nm, is in excellent agreement with the length of the molecule, 1.52 nm, determined with a molecular modelling program (Spartan®08 V 1.0.0).

Figure S2. Break-off distance histogram for compound **1**.

b.4. Conductance values of other molecular junctions determined by the I(s) method for comparison with **1**

Table I. Conductance values determined by the I(s) method for the indicated molecular junctions on gold.

Molecule	SMC (G_0)	Reference
	$L = 2.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ $H = 3.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$	<i>This work</i>
	$4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	8
	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	7
	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	9
	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-5}$	10
	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	9
	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	9

$2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$

6

b.5. Break Junction (BJ) measurements

In the break junction (BJ) technique, the STM gold tip was driven into contact with the gold surface and then immediately withdrawn while monitoring the current as a function of the distance. More than 1500 curves were recorded using this method. Some representative current-distance retraction curves recorded using the BJ method, which show peak-like events are presented in Figure S3.

Figure S3. a) Seven representative chosen BJ curves. b) 0.5 nm horizontally shifted BJ curves showing peak-like shape events.

BJ retraction curves have been analyzed using the same statistical method described in the main text for the $I(s)$ method to produce pie charts. These charts display the fractions of retraction events which respectively give peak-like events curves, plateau-like shape $I(s)$ curves as well as those that do not show distinctive events. Such an analysis is presented in Figure S4 for 1558 break-junction recorded traces of compound **1**. This analysis displays the percentages corresponding to each of the observed indicated events. Note that although a measurable percentage of the events correspond to peak featuring ones, the fraction of such events is considerably less than for the $I(s)$ method whose results are presented in the main manuscript (Figure 2). A tentative explanation for this can be found in the very different morphologies of the gold contacts that are likely to result from $I(s)$ and BJ formation, respectively. In the $I(s)$ method contact between the gold STM tip and the surface is avoided; when the junction is formed the pyrazolyl moiety is more likely to attach to the STM tip in the protonated

form and to evolve to the deprotonated one before detaching, which results in a high conductance state on the contact: a peak-like event (see model in main text: under scenario A). On the contrary, in the BJ method there is a direct contact between the gold STM tip and the surface, which results in the formation of a chain of gold atoms as the tip is retracted until this chain of gold atoms breaks. In this situation, it is suggested that the pyrazolyl group could be more likely to bind co-facially to the STM tip in the protonated form and then to evolve to the deprotonated one and finally to bind to the STM tip before detaching. This scenario corresponds to plateau-like events as it was demonstrated by DFT calculations (see scenario B in the main text).

Figure S4. Junction formation statistics for 1558 *Break-junction* recorded traces of compound 1. **(a)** Percentages corresponding to each of the observed indicated events. **(b)** Percentages determined considering only traces where molecular junctions are considered to have been formed.

c. Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations

c.1. Geometry of isolated molecules and their junctions

The DFT code (SIESTA) was used to obtain fully relaxed geometries of the isolated molecules (protonated and de-protonated) in the junction (video S1), as shown in Figure S5.

Figure S5. Fully relaxed isolated molecules in the two cases considered in this contribution, i.e., protonated molecule (top panel), and de-protonated (bottom panel).

Then, the molecules were connected to gold electrodes, see for instance Video S1, in two different configurations, (a) and (b) as shown in Figure S6. For each binding configuration, both protonated and de-protonated molecules were investigated (the red circle shows the proton, which is either present or absent).

Figure S6. Cartoon showing the two configurations considered: a) Direct contact (non-co-facial). b) Co-facial contact. Both configurations include a protonated molecule (left), and a de-protonated one (right).

[Video S1.avi](#)

Video S1. Full optimization process for the molecule together with the representative leads, i.e. the 'extended molecule'.

c.2. Binding energy of protonated and de-protonated molecules on gold

To calculate the optimum binding distance for protonated and deprotonated molecules between two gold (111) surfaces, we used DFT and the counterpoise method, which removes basis set superposition errors (BSSE). The binding distance z is defined as the distance between the gold surface and the N atom of the molecule. Here the protonated or de-protonated molecule is defined as monomer A and the gold electrodes as monomer B. Thus, the minimum binding energy for each monomer was determined and subsequently the same basis sets and functionals were used for optimization. After finding the optimum distance between the anchor group (N) and the leads (Au), the molecule was allowed to fully relax between the electrodes, see video S1. Moreover, what is shown in Figure S6 is a fully optimized junction (290 junctions). The binding

distance z was calculated following this procedure for the two different considered states of the molecule, i.e. with and without the H atom.

The ground state energy of the total system, calculated using SIESTA, is denoted as E_{AB}^{AB} , with the parameters defined as those in the main text. Here the gold leads consist of 3 layers of 25 atoms. The energy of each monomer is then calculated in a fixed basis, which is achieved through the use of ghost atoms in SIESTA. Hence the energy of the individual molecule in the presence of the fixed basis is defined as E_A^{AB} and for the gold is E_B^{AB} . The binding energy is then calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Binding Energy} = E_{AB}^{AB} - E_A^{AB} - E_B^{AB} \quad (1)$$

First, we calculated the binding energy for case-a, Figure S6.a., i.e. the direct, non-co-facial contact. Figure S7 shows that the de-protonated molecules (without H), exhibit a stronger bind to the gold electrode. The binding energy calculated for the co-facial contact (Figure S6.b) is shown in Figure S8.

Figure S7. Left panel: Binding energy for the two molecule configurations as a function of molecule-contact distance. The equilibrium distance (i.e. the minimum of the binding energy curve) is found to be approximately 2.4 Å for the de- protonated and 2.5 Å for the protonated molecule. **Right panels:** Scheme of protonated and de-protonated molecules attached to gold leads (direct contact).

Figure S8. Left panel: Binding energy of both molecule configurations to gold as a function of molecule-contact distance. The equilibrium distance (i.e. the minimum of the binding energy curve) is found to be approximately 2.6 Å for the de-protonated and 2.9 Å for the protonated molecule. Right panels: Scheme of the protonated and de-protonated molecule configurations attached to gold leads (co-facial contact).

c.3. Wave function plots for isolated molecules

The plots below show iso-surfaces of the HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 of isolated protonated or half-deprotonated molecules.

Figure S9. Wave function for the protonated molecule. Top panel: Fully optimised geometry of the protonated molecule. Lower panel: HOMO and LUMO with their energies and HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 with their energies.

Figure S10. Wave function for the half de-protonated molecule. **Top panel:** Fully optimised for the half deprotonated molecule. **Lower panel:** HOMO and LUMO with their energies, and HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 with their energies.

From Figures S9 and S10 we see that the de-protonated ring has more weight than the protonated ring, which supports the binding energy calculations (see Figures S7 and S8).

After the final step in the deprotonation process both anchor rings are fully de-protonated and the weight is distributed equally on both anchors, as shown in Figure S11.

Figure S11. Wave function for the fully de-protonated molecule. **Top panel:** Fully optimised for the complete de-protonated molecule. **Lower panel:** HOMO and LUMO with their energies, and HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 with their energies.

c.4. Theoretical model for de-protonating process

To follow the effect of deprotonation, the next plots show the effect of moving the two H atoms gradually away from the nitrogen atoms on the transmission coefficient (see top panel of Figure S12).

Figure S12. Zero bias transmission coefficient, $T(E)$ of de-protonation model, 0 when H atom is present (black solid-line) and 7 when H is far away from the N atom.

The lower panel of Figure S12 shows the effect of the de-protonation process. During successive de-protonation steps the transmission curves move from lower energy (protonated molecule) to high energy for the de-protonated molecule (black solid-line to red solid-line). Transport through the protonated molecule is therefore LUMO dominated at DFT predicted Fermi energy ($E_F=0$), whereas the de-protonated molecule is HOMO dominated.

c.5. Electron transfer

Switching from HOMO to LUMO means that some electrons are transferred from the electrodes to both molecule configurations (protonated and de-protonated) and nitrogen atoms act as an anchor group. Figure S13 shows the four nitrogen atoms and their numbers.

Figure S13. Numbering system for the 4 nitrogen atoms.

Table S.II shows the number of electrons gained by the four nitrogen atoms (see Figure S13 for the numbering convention). The number of electrons on 1 and 2 nitrogen atoms barely changes when the molecule is de-protonated, whereas atoms 3 and 4 gain electrons.

Table S.II. Number of electrons gained by the 4 nitrogen atoms.

	Number of electrons gained by the 4 nitrogen atoms				
	1	2	4	4	Total
Protonated	0.138	0.176	0.088	0.083	0.485
Deprotonated	0.136	0.176	0.153	0.180	0.645

Table S.III shows the number of electrons gained by the whole molecule, the number gained by the four nitrogen atoms and each atom within the molecule in terms of gaining or losing electrons. It is clear that deprotonated molecules gain more electrons than the protonated ones (i.e. third and fifth row in this table).

Molecule	Number of outer shell	Number of outer shell	Mulliken gain in number	Number of electrons	Electrons gained (+)
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	electrons on the 4 nitrogens in gas phase	electrons on the 4 nitrogens in the junction	of electrons on the 4 nitrogens	gained by the whole molecule in the junction from the gold	or lost (-) by each atom within the molecule
Protonated	4 X 5 = 20.0	4N= 20.485	0.485	0.601	C=0.136 H=-0.02
Deprotonated	4 X 5 = 20.0	4N= 20.645	0.645	0.699	C=0.201 H=-0.147
Protonated	4 X 5 = 20.0	4N= 20.489	0.489	0.685	C=0.296 H=-0.100
Deprotonated	4 X 5 = 20.0	4N= 20.625	0.625	0.698	C=0.269 H=-0.196

c.6. Spin polarization

In this section, the possibility of spin polarization is investigated by calculating the spin-up and spin-down transmission coefficients for the four configurations. Two of the four configurations are co-facial contact including protonated ($P_{cof.}$) and de-protonated ($D_{cof.}$) as shown on the right of Figure S14, the other two are non-co-facial and again protonated ($P_{cof.}$) and de-protonated ($D_{cof.}$).

Figure S14. Cartoon illustrating four binding configurations: a protonated molecule (P_{tip}) attached to a gold tip; a de-protonated molecule (D_{tip}) attached to a gold tip; a protonated molecule ($P_{cof.}$) attached cofacially to a gold tip, and a de-protonated molecule ($D_{cof.}$) attached cofacially to a gold tip.

For the first configuration in Figure S14, P_{tip} , the protonated molecule is attached to the gold tip; this type of contact is named as non-co-facial. Looking at spin-

up curve and spin-down on Figure S15 no spin polarization occurs, since the two curves are identical.

Figure S15. Transmission coefficients, $T(E)$, for the binding configuration of P_{tip} , the two curves represent the spin-up and spin-down.

The second configuration is the de-protonated molecule, D_{tip} , attached to a gold tip, this type of contact is again a non-co-facial one. No spin polarization effect is observed, as shown in Figure S16.

Figure S16. Transmission coefficients, $T(E)$, for the binding configuration of D_{tip} , the two curves represent the spin-up and spin-down.

The last two configurations are co-facial contact for protonated and de-protonated molecules (P_{tip} and D_{tip}) cofacially attached to a gold tip (on the right of Figure S14); this type of contact will be called henceforward a co-facial contact. Figures S17 and S18 confirm that no spin polarization effect is observed.

Figure S17. Transmission coefficients, $T(E)$, for the binding configuration of P_{cof} , the two curves represent the spin-up and spin-down.

Figure S18. Transmission coefficients, $T(E)$, for the binding configuration of D_{cof} , the two curves represent the spin-up and spin-down.

d. Fabrication of Langmuir-Blodgett films

LB films were prepared in a KSV Nima KN 2003 trough with dimensions 580 x 145 mm², housed at constant temperature (20 °C) in a clean room. A Wilhelmy paper plate pressure sensor was used to measure the surface pressure (π) of the monolayer. Two different subphases were used: pure water (Millipore Milli-Q, 18.2 M Ω ·cm, pH = 5.6) and aqueous NaOH solution (pH = 11.0). 3.0 mL of a $2.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M solution of compound **1** in THF:CHCl₃ (1:4), was spread onto the aqueous subphase. After waiting for at least 30 minutes for solvent evaporation, the mechanical barrier compression started with an initial area per molecule of 1.49 nm²·molecule⁻¹. The compression speed

was $6 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. Under these experimental conditions, reproducible isotherms (π - A) were obtained (see Figure S19).

Figure S19. Surface pressure (π) vs area per molecule (A) isotherms recorded at 20°C onto a pure water subphase ($\text{pH} = 5.6$) or a NaOH aqueous solution ($\text{pH} = 11.0$).

The monolayers at the air-water interface were transferred onto solid supports at a constant area per molecule of 0.21 nm^2 by the vertical dipping method (dipping speed was $2 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) onto Au(111) substrates.

e. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (^1H NMR)

The right panel in Figure 5 (main paper) shows, for comparison purposes, at the top the ^1H -NMR spectra of a reference compound, namely, 3,5-dimethylpyrazole, at the bottom a dispersion of un-protected gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) in water prepared as reported elsewhere,¹¹ and the figure in the middle is the spectrum of a mixture of the two solutions. All the spectra were measured in dimethyl sulfoxide- d_6 ($\text{C}_2\text{D}_6\text{OS}$), on a Bruker AV-400 MHz equipment. The proton corresponding to the pyrrole-like nitrogen of the pyrazole unit is located at ca. 12 ppm. Such a peak clearly disappears (while the other signals in the molecule remain in the same position) when uncapped Au nanoparticles are added to the solution. Figures S20, S21 and S22 show magnifications of these spectra, and their signal assignment.

Figure S20. ¹H-NMR spectrum of 3,5-dimethylpyrazole in DMSO-d₆ together with the hydrogen signal assignment.

Figure S21. ¹H-NMR spectrum of uncapped gold nanoparticles prepared in aqueous solution (Milli-Q). Spectrum recorded in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S22. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of 3,5-dimethylpyrazole mixed with uncapped gold nanoparticles. Spectrum recorded in DMSO-d_6 .

f. References

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